

HEART DISEASE PREDICTION USING MACHINE LEARNING TECHNOLOGIES

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Abstract - Heart disease is one of the most significant causes of mortality in the world today. Prediction of cardiovascular disease is a critical challenge in the area of clinical data analysis. Machine learning (ML) has been shown to be effective in assisting in making decisions and predictions from the large quantity of data produced by the healthcare industry. We have also seen ML techniques being used in recent developments in different areas of the Internet of Things (IoT). Various studies give only a glimpse into predicting heart disease with ML techniques. In this paper, we propose a novel method that aims at finding significant features by applying machine learning techniques resulting in improving the accuracy in the prediction of cardiovascular disease. The prediction model is introduced with different combinations of features and several known classification techniques. We produce an enhanced performance level with an accuracy level of 88.7% through the prediction model for heart disease with the hybrid random forest with a linear model (HRFLM).

I. INTRODUCTION

It is difficult to identify heart disease because of several contributory risk factors such as diabetes, high blood pressure, high cholesterol, abnormal pulse rate and many other factors. Various techniques in data mining and neural networks have been employed to find out the severity of heart disease among humans. The severity of the disease is classified based on various methods like K-Nearest Neighbor Algorithm (KNN), Decision Trees (DT), Logistic Regression (LR), and Support Vector Machine (SVM). The nature of heart disease is complex and hence, the disease must be handled carefully. Not doing so may affect the heart or cause premature death. The perspective of medical science and data mining are used for discovering various sorts of metabolic syndromes. Data mining with classification plays a significant role in the prediction of heart disease and data investigation.

II. BACKGROUND AND OBJECTIVES

The importance and advantages of the application of Machine learning based heart disease detection and prediction system were discussed in several research findings. The application of artificial intelligence in disease detection system especially the cardiac disease system detection improves the performance of other existing widely used models like models provided by American College of Cardiology / American Heart Association (ACC / AHA) models in CVD detection and prediction [4]. The possibility and related matters of providing advanced services of a human health management system were analyzed by Zhao, Wang, and Nakahira, in 2011 and they had also given a research direction of medical technology on IoT [5]. Many types of health-related sensors and technologies were analyzed by them. They identified some issues which need to be solved. The home monitoring system and decision support system was schemed by Chiuchisan and Geman in 2014 [6]. This system contributed to home monitoring, diagnosis, medical prescriptions, medical treatment, rehabilitation and development of his patients with Parkinson's disease. Wireless Health Monitoring System (WHMS) has attracted considerable attention from the research community and industry over the last decade. Improvement of several Machine learning algorithms and classifier performances like weighted associative classifier were reported in the detection of cardiac abnormalities [7].

The elderly patients monitoring from indoor or outdoor locations had been presented by a real-time mobile healthcare system in [3]. A signal sensor and a smartphone were the primary components of the system. The bio-signal sensor data was transmitted to an intelligent server via GPRS / UMTS network for data collection. The system could perform in monitoring the mobility, vital signs, location, and condition of the elderly patient from a distant location. A fully functional wireless body area network (WBAN) system had been proposed in [8]. The designed system used medical bands to obtain physiological data from sensors. The author had chosen some medical bands in order to abate the interruption between the sensors and other existing devices. To increase the operating extent, the multi-hopping technique had been implemented and a medical gateway wireless board had been used in this regard.

Manpreet Singh et al. [9] designed a heart disease prediction system based on Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) and Fuzzy Cognitive Map (FCM). They validated the data of the Canadian Community Health Survey (CCHS) 2012 dataset. They used twenty significant attributes. To generate the weight matrix for the FCM model, SEM was used which then predicted a possibility of cardiovascular diseases. An SEM model is defined with the correlation between CCC 121 along with 20 attributes; here CCC 121 is a variable which defines whether the respondent has heart disease. Prajakta Ghadge et al. [10] researched an intelligent heart attack prediction system using big data. Heart attack needs to be diagnosed timely and effectively because of its high prevalence. The main objective of this research article was to find a prototype of an intelligent heart attack prediction system that uses big data and data mining modeling techniques. This system could gather hidden knowledge concerning heart disease from a given heart disease database.

This work aims in developing a Decision Support System in heart disease detection that uses the data mining technique having best accuracy and performance among Naïve Bayes, Support Vector Machine, Simple Logistic Regression, Random Forest & Artificial Neural Network (ANN) etc. By using several cardiovascular system parameters such as age, blood pressure, ECG results, sex, and blood sugar, it is possible to measure the possibility of getting affected by heart disease [11]. For deriving the algorithm with the best accuracy in the detection and prediction of heart disease, a comparative analysis of chosen machine learning algorithms has been shown. This algorithm takes the medical parameters such as age, blood pressure, heartbeat, sex, ECG results, blood sugar etc. as input and shows the probability of getting affected by heart disease as output. This proposed system comprises the scheme and design of a web-based android application which uses an efficient machine learning technique to detect heart disease. It can serve as a very useful tool for doctors, patients, and medical students to diagnose heart disease. For diagnosis of fatal physiological conditions and symptoms such as heart attack requires 24 hours monitoring of patient's health after transferring from hospital to home. Using this application, the patient can input the current parameters of heart disease from anywhere on the application interface and view the risk level of getting heart disease. All of the parameters that are not real-time like blood sugar, Serum cholesterol, ECG results will be available in the doctor's prescribed report and there are some parameters like chest pain type and exercise-induced angina, which have to be self-measured periodically by the patient and input the values manually on the application interface. If any fatal situation is detected by the application, the patient can communicate with any doctor via video call and any registered doctor related to heart disease can be found by putting his phone number in the search bar.

In hospitals, there are provisions for continuous monitoring of critical care heart patients whereas after the release from the hospital patients normally go out of direct supervision. These patients need continuous monitoring of their health condition to reduce the risks of unwanted complications at least for a week or so. Hence, another objective of this work is the empirical design and implementation of the prototype of a continuous real-time cardiac health

monitoring system by using Arduino based sensors, which can be developed commercially so that it can be attached to the patient's body. The sensor data can be transmitted to the server using the Wi-Fi module and saved in the server database. The sensor data can be updated every 10 seconds in the server and doctors with smartphones can view his patient's updated health status by using this application from anywhere. While any value of the heartbeat, temperature or humidity sensors goes beyond the threshold value, doctors will receive an alert message in the application as well as his phone instantly. Besides, family members and caretakers can also visualize the patient's real-time data through the application and if the patient remains in the ICU, the buzzer in the Arduino will alert them even though in case of network failure. When a patient will need consultancy or medication from a doctor from another distant location of the world, he/she can simply start live video streaming through the application.

III. PROPOSED SYSTEM

In this study, we have used an *R* studio rattle to perform heart disease classification of the Cleveland UCI repository. It provides an easy-to-use visual representation of the dataset, working environment and building the predictive analytics. ML process starts from a pre-processing data phase followed by feature selection based on DT entropy, classification of modeling performance evaluation, and the results with improved accuracy. The feature selection and modeling keep on repeating for various combinations of attributes. The UCI dataset detailed information with attributes used. The performance of each model generated based on 13 features and ML techniques used for each iteration and performance are recorded. Section A summarizes the data pre-processing, Section B discusses the feature selection using entropy, Section C explains the classification with ML techniques and Section D presented for the performance of the results. Heart disease data is pre-processed after collection of various records. The dataset contains a total of 303 patient records, where 6 records are with some missing values. Those 6 records have been removed from the dataset and the remaining 297 patient records are used in pre-processing. The multiclass variable and binary classification are introduced for the attributes of the given dataset.

IV. MODULES

A. Upload Training Data

The process of rule generation advances in two stages. During the first stage, the SVM model is built using training data during each fold, this model is utilized for predicting the class labels. The rules are evaluated on the remaining 10% of test data for determining the accuracy, precision, recall and F-measure. In addition, rule set size and mean rule length are also calculated for each fold of cross-validation.

B. Data Pre-Processing

Heart disease data is pre-processed after collection of various records. The dataset contains a total of 303 patient records, where 6 records are with some missing values. Those 6 records have been removed from the dataset and the remaining 297 patient records are used in pre-processing. The multiclass variable and binary classification are introduced for the attributes of the given dataset.

C. Predicting Heart Disease

The training set is different from test set. In this study, we used this method to verify the universal applicability of the methods. In k-fold cross validation method, the whole dataset is used to train and test the classifier to Heart stroke.

D. Graphical Representations

The analyses of proposed systems are calculated based on the approvals and disapprovals. This can be measured with the help of graphical notations such as pie chart, bar chart and line chart. The data can be given in a dynamical data.

V. ALGORITHM

Decision Tree

Decision tree is a basic classification and regression method. Decision tree model has a tree structure, which can describe the process of classification instances based on features. It can be considered as a set of if-then rules, which also can be thought of as conditional probability distributions defined in feature space and class space.

Random Forest

RF is a classification by using many decision trees. This algorithm proposed by Breiman RF is a multifunctional Machine Learning method. It can perform the tasks of prediction and regression. In addition, RF is based on bagging and it plays an important role in ensemble Machine Learning. RF has been employed in several biomedicine research.

RF generates many decision trees, which is very different from decision tree algorithm. When the RF is predicting a new object based on some attributes, each tree in RF will give its own classification result and 'vote' and then the overall output of the forest will be the largest number of taxonomy. In the regression problem, the RF output is the average value of output of all decision trees.

Support Vector Machine

Support Vector Machine (SVM) is a supervised machine learning algorithm which can be used for both classification or regression challenges. However, it is mostly used in classification problems. In this algorithm, we plot each data item as a point in n-dimensional space (where n is number of features you have) with the value of each feature being the value of a particular coordinate. Then, we perform classification by finding the hyper-plane that differentiate the two classes very well (look at the below snapshot). The SVM algorithm is implemented in practice using a kernel. The learning of the hyper plane in linear SVM is done by transforming the problem using some linear algebra, which is out of the scope of this introduction to SVM. A powerful insight is that the linear SVM can be rephrased using the inner product of any two given observations, rather than the observations themselves. The inner product between two vectors is the sum of the multiplication of each pair of input values. For example, the inner product of the vectors [2, 3] and [5, 6] is $2*5 + 3*6$ or 28. The equation for making a prediction for a new input using the dot product between the input (x) and each support vector (xi) is calculated as follows:

$$\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}) = \mathbf{B0} + \text{sum}(\mathbf{ai} * (\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{xi}))$$

This is an equation that involves calculating the inner products of a new input vector (x) with all support vectors in training data. The coefficients B0 and ai (for each input) must be estimated from the training data by the learning algorithm.

VI. SYSTEM DESIGN

1 ARCHITECTURE DIAGRAM

2 COMPONENT DIAGRAM

a User

b Admin

3 ER DIAGRAM

a User

b Admin

4 USE CASE DIAGRAM

a User

b Admin

5 DATA FLOW DIAGRAM
a User

b Admin

8 CONCLUSION

Identifying the processing of raw healthcare data of heart information will help in the long term saving of human lives and early detection of abnormalities in heart conditions. Machine learning techniques were used in this work to process raw data and provide a new and novel discernment towards heart disease. Heart disease prediction is challenging and very important in the medical. However, the mortality rate can be drastically controlled if the disease is detected at the early stages and preventative measures are adopted as soon as possible. Further extension of this study is highly desirable to direct the investigations to real-world datasets instead of just theoretical approaches and simulations. The proposed hybrid HRFLM approach is used combining the characteristics of Random Forest (RF) and Linear Method (LM). HRFLM proved to be quite accurate in the prediction of heart disease. The future course of this research can be performed with diverse mixtures of machine learning techniques to better prediction techniques. Furthermore, new feature selection methods can be developed to get a broader perception of the significant features to increase the performance of heart disease prediction.

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